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Selected Variables as Predictors of Quality Education Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated selected variables as predictors of quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population for the study comprised 8,924 teachers. A sample of 540 teachers were drawn from the population through multi-stage sampling approach and used for the study. Two instruments titled “Selected Variables Scale” (SVS) and “Quality Education Delivery Scale” (QEDS) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts in measurement and evaluation. The reliability coefficients of the instruments obtained for (SVS) was 0.76 and (QEDS) was 0.87 respectively. The researchers and two research assistants administered the instruments to the respondents and data collected were answered using simple regression statistics for the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using ANOVA associated with regression which were subjected to critical probability value at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The result shows that: management of classroom environment, management of teacher-student cordiality and teachers’ knowledge of subject matter predicted quality education delivery in public secondary school in Rivers State, independently taken. Based on the findings of this study conclusion and recommendations were drawn.

Keywords: Selected Variable, Education, Quality Education Delivery and School

INTRODUCTION

One of the major goals of every teaching and learning process is to ensure proper acquisition of knowledge or skill and this could be achieved through adequate education delivery. Sabastine (2020) explained that the essence of instructional delivery is to positively affect the knowledge and understanding of the learner. Most importantly, learners develop academically when they are well exposed to learning through the use of appropriate learning procedure. Ojo (2019) stressed that when learning instructions are well delivered in school among learners, it positively promotes their academic well-being and also help in the measurement of quality of education delivery in school. Nwankwo (2021) noted that teachers, educational planners and other stakeholders in the educational sector must be conscious of how well instruction are delivered in school so as to realized the goal of quality education delivery among learners.

Quality education delivery means the use of necessary human and non-human resources to achieve the objective of learning which is observable in the behaviour of the learner. Quality education delivery

affects positively the skill, value, knowledge and attitude of the learners. Stressing on the need for quality education delivery, James (2019) opined that it helps the educationist to know the extent educational objectives at various levels of education have been achieved, it also helps in positive modification of elements or factors that could enhance teaching and learning in school. He also stated that the quality of manpower and positive societal growth and development could be used to measure quality education delivery, positive contributions of ideas by learners in learning and other related activities, increase in participation of learners in subsequent learning are all indicators of quality education delivery. Meanwhile, there are a lot of variables that could positively or negatively affect quality education delivery, but among all, the researcher in this study considered management of classroom environment, management of teacher-students' cordiality and teachers' knowledge of subject matter.

Management of classroom environment entails the availability of classroom equipment that could enhance delivery of teaching and learning. Classroom environment that could enhance teaching and learning should contain proper chair, desk, projectors and normal classroom population and so on. When classrooms are provided with the required learning facilities then, delivery of learning becomes more effective.

Teacher's relationship with students remains a central factor that could positively or negatively affect quality education delivery in teaching and learning process in school. Teacher-student relationship is a process whereby a teacher uses verbal and non-verbal cues to reduce fearfulness or feeling of shyness and negative perception towards the teacher, so as to enable learners feel free during classroom interaction. It is one of the major tools that sustain learners' interest in school and subjects.

Knowledge of subject matter is very necessary for a teacher to be fully knowledgeable about the concepts, theory or topics to be taught to learners in the classroom. For teaching and learning to achieve its goal of adequate transmission of values, skills, competencies and attitude to the learners knowledge, the teacher must be well knowledgeable in his or her area of subject specialization. Teaching is an activity that requires proper and indebt understanding of what to be taught and how to properly achieve learning objectives at the end of each classroom interaction. Omenibi (2018) stressed that for teaching and learning to be interesting and, for learners to have proper understanding of the materials learnt, the classroom teacher must have proper understanding of the topic or subject he or she is teaching. Knowledge of subject matter include knowing the subject or topic to be taught properly, making the lesson very interesting to the understanding of learners and proper evaluation of learning at the end of each teaching and learning activities. Any Teacher that lacks the knowledge of subject matter ends-up not passing proper teaching experience of appropriate skills, values and knowledge to the learners and this in most case affect academic performance of the affected learners and even affects their future academic endeavour. It also entails knowing what to teach, how to teach and how to ensure that learners understand what is being taught. Having proper knowledge of the subject matter, makes teaching very easy for the teacher. It increases performance in the teaching life span of a teacher and makes teaching an appreciable carrier at all times. The ability of a teacher to teach learners confidently, carryout proper assessment of learners in a given subject area and proper answering of questions from learners ensures knowledge of subject matter.

Okoye (2022) explained that when quality education delivery is achieved in teaching and learning process, it enhances the academic performance of learners and also help in ascertaining the achievement of academic goal of education. Obia (2017) emphasized that in order for schools and its personnel to achieve quality education delivery, some variables must be appropriately held on constant. Some variables could positively or negatively predict quality education delivery in school. It is against this background that the researcher conceived the idea to investigate some selected variables as predictors of quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The educational development of learners has become a major source of concern to various individuals in the society including the Government and non-governmental agencies. This they have been demonstrating

through provision of necessary human and non-human facilities such as school buildings, employment of qualified manpower, provision of laboratory, library, recreational facilities, classroom desk and so on. However, these efforts have not yielded the much desired positive out-come especially among learners in public secondary schools in Rivers State as noticed by the researchers in recent time.

There are consistent cases of poor performance of learners in their internal and external examination such as mid-term and result of their West African Senior School Certificate Examination. This could result from poor quality learning delivery to these learners in their school arising from poor knowledge of subject matter by their teachers, poor management of classroom environment and poor cordial relationship between teachers and students in school.

This situation is on the increase on a yearly basis in the area and it is causing the affected students to drop out from school and others engaging in various deviant behaviours such as cultism and stealing etc. If education much achieve its goal of human development, then the issue of quality of education delivery must be properly addressed. The problem of this study therefore, is to examine if some selected variables predict quality education deliver in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the extent to which some selected variables predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The objectives are to:

3. determine if the management of classroom environment predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. investigate if the management of teacher-student cordiality predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
5. determine if teachers' knowledge of subject matter predict quality education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

- (1) To what extent does management of classroom environment predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- (2) To what extent does management of teacher-student cordiality predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- (3) To what extent does teachers' knowledge of subject matter predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 alpha level guided the study.

- H₁ Management of classroom environment does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H₂ Management of teacher-student cordiality does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H₃ Teachers' knowledge of subject matter does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted correlational research design. The population for the study comprised all the 8,924 teachers in the 276 public senior secondary schools in the 23 Local Government Area of Rivers State (source, Rivers State Ministry of Education 2022/2023 teachers' enrolment figure). The sample for the study was 540 teachers. Multi-stage sampling procedures were adopted for proper representation of the subjects. In doing this, simple random sampling technique was used to draw 16 local government area of the 23 local government areas in Rivers State. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw 4 secondary schools from each of the local government area. Then, proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw the teachers in each of the sampled schools and used for the study.

The instruments for the study were two self-developed questionnaires titled “Selected Variables Scale” (SVS) and “Quality Education Delivery Scale” (QEDS). The Selected Variables Scale consist 34 items measuring different variables such as management of classroom environment, teachers-student cordiality and teachers’ knowledge of subject matter. The Quality Education Delivery Scale (QEDS) consist of 36 items measuring various quality education delivery. However, all items in this scale were structured based on the four point modified likert rating scale of Strongly Agree = (SA), Agree = (A), Disagree = (D) and Strongly Disagree = (SD) which were assigned numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 for positively keyed items while 1, 2, 3 and 4 were assigned to negatively keyed items respectively. The validity of the instruments (SVS) and (QEDS) were determined based on face and content validities.

The reliability coefficients of the instruments (SVS) and (QEDS) were estimated using the cronbach alpha reliability estimate and reliability coefficient was 0.76 for SVS and 0.87 for QEDS respectively. This shows that the coefficient values of the instruments are high and good enough for use for this study. However, the researcher worked with one research assistant in each school (Principals) who were properly guided about the instruments. The copies of the questionnaire were administered on the teachers and were successfully collected immediately after administration.

The research questions were answered using Simple Regression Statistics. However, the hypotheses were tested using ANOVA associated with regression which were subjected to critical probability value at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

RESULTS

The results were presented on the tables as follows:

Research Question 1: *To what extent does management of classroom environment predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: simple regression on the extent management of classroom environment predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.146 ^a	.021	.019	6.60654

a. Predictors: (Constant), management of classroom environment

Table 1 shows that there is a very low relationship between management of classroom environment on the prediction of quality education delivery (R= 0.15) The Adjusted R square value=0.019 shows that only 19% of the variation in the quality education delivery can be explained by management of classroom environment. The remaining 81% in the variation in their quality education delivery can be attributed to other factors not included in the model.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does management of teacher-student cordiality predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple regression on the extent management of teacher-student cordiality predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.153 ^a	.023	.021	6.59928

a. Predictors: (Constant), management of teacher-student cordiality

Table 2 shows that there is a low positive relation between management of teacher-student cordiality on the prediction of quality education delivery $R=0.153$. The adjusted R square value= 0.021 . This implies that 2.1% of the variation in the quality education delivery can be explained by the management of teacher-student cordiality while the remaining 97.7 % can be due to other factors not included in this model

Research Question 3: *To what extent does teachers' knowledge of subject matter predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple regression on the extent teachers' knowledge of subject matter predict quality education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.327 ^a	.107	.105	6.31009

a. Predictors: (Constant), teachers' knowledge of subject matter

Table 3 shows that there is a low positive relationship between teachers' knowledge of subject matter on the prediction of quality education delivery ($R= 0.32$). With an Adjusted R-square value of -0.105 , it implies that 10.5% of the variation in the quality education delivery can be explained by the teachers' knowledge of subject matter while the remaining 89.5% can be due to other factors not included in this model

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Management of classroom environment does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: ANOVA associated with simple regression on the prediction of classroom environment on quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4a

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	378.825	1	378.825	8.679	.003 ^b
	Residual	17371.267	538	43.646		
	Total	17750.093	539			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality education delivery

b. Predictors: (Constant), Management of classroom environment

The ANOVA table shows that the prediction is significant ($F=8.68$, $DF=1, 418$, $p<0.05$). Therefore H_0 is rejected, implying that Management of classroom environment significantly predicts quality education delivery in Rivers State.

Table 4b

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	54.101	3.069		17.631	.000
	Management of classroom environment	.273	.093	.146	2.946	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Quality education delivery

Table 4b shows that for every increase by 1 SD in the Management of classroom environment scores there will be an increase of 0.15 SD in the Quality education delivery score.

Hypothesis 2: Management of teacher-student cordiality does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: ANOVA associated with simple regression on the prediction of Management of teacher-student cordiality on quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 5a

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	416.979	1	416.979	9.575	.002 ^b
Residual	17333.113	538	43.551		
Total	17750.093	539			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality education delivery

b. Predictors: (Constant), Management of teacher-student cordiality

Table 5a shows that the prediction is significant (F=9.56, DF=1, 418, p<0.05), hence HO2 which state that Management of teacher-student cordiality does not significantly predict quality education delivery is rejected.

Table 5b

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	56.234	2.240		25.107	.000
	Management of teacher-student cordiality	.266	.086	.153	3.094	.002

a. dependent variable: Quality education delivery

Table 5b shows that for every increase by 1SD in the management of teacher-student cordiality score of the students, there will be an increase of 0.15 SD in the quality education delivery.

Hypothesis 3: Teachers' knowledge of subject matter does not significantly predict quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: ANOVA associated with simple regression on the prediction of teachers' knowledge of subject matter on quality education delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6a

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1902.809	1	1902.809	47.789	.000 ^b
Residual	15847.283	538	39.817		
Total	17750.093	539			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality education delivery

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers' knowledge of subject matter

Table 9a shows that the prediction is significant (F= 47.79, df=1, 418, p<0.05), hence HO3 is rejected. This implies that teachers' knowledge of subject matter significantly predict quality education delivery.

Table 6b:

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	50.981	1.780	28.647	.000
	teachers' knowledge of subject matter	.448	.065	.327	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Quality education delivery

Table 6b shows that for every increase by 1 SD in the teachers' knowledge of subject matter score, there will be a decrease of 0.33SD in the quality education delivery score of the students.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study are summarized as shown below:

1. It was shown that management of classroom environment significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. It was found that management of teacher's students' relationship significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. The study showed that teachers' knowledge of subject matter independently significantly predicted quality education delivery in Public secondary school in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Discussion of findings was based on the summary of findings.

The finding of research question one and hypothesis one indicates that management of classroom environment significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary school in Rivers State. This indicates that, while the scores of classroom environment were increasing, the scores of quality education delivery were also increasing. This finding stressed the need for teachers to always be conversant with their classroom environment and be sure that it does not negatively affect teaching and learning in school. This finding is in agreement with that of Ogunyani (2019) who found that there is significant relationship between classroom environment and quality education delivery in schools. However, this result was not supported by that of Johnson (2017) who found that there is no significant relationship between classroom environment and quality education delivery among teachers in schools. The difference in these findings could be due to different sample size and population used in the two studies.

The findings of research question two and hypothesis two shows that teachers'-students' cordiality significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State. This also means that as scores of teacher-student cordiality increases, that of quality education delivery was also increasing. This implies that an enhanced relationship between teachers and students always engender positive academic success in school and quality service delivery among students and teachers respectively. This finding is supported by that of Isaac (2018) who found that there is significant relationship between teacher-student cordiality and quality education delivery based on gender. Meanwhile, this result is not supported by that of Dokubo (2020) who found that there is no significant relationship between teacher-student cordiality and quality education delivery in schools. The difference in these findings could be due to different sample size.

The findings of research question three and hypothesis three reviewed that teachers' knowledge of subject matter independently significantly predicted quality education delivery in Public secondary schools in Rivers State. This result shows that as the scores of teaches' knowledge of subject matter was increasing that of quality education delivery was also increasing. This means that there is need for teachers to be very knowledgeable in their subject area so as to enhance proper teaching of learners in school. This finding is in agreement with that of Kali (2020) who found a significant relationship between knowledge

of subject matter and quality education service delivery. However, this finding is not in agreement with that of Osuji (2019) who found that there was no significant relationship between knowledge of subject matter and quality education delivery.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion were drawn; management of classroom environment significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary school in Rivers State. it was found that management of teacher-students' cordiality significantly independently predicted quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State and the study showed that teachers' knowledge of subject matter independently significantly predicted quality education delivery in Public secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were drawn based on the findings of this study;

1. Teachers should always ensure that they are fully in control of classroom activities including the learners and other learning materials during teaching and learning process.
2. Teachers should ensure that they are well prepared during any instructional activity. This will help them to have proper knowledge of what to teach and also achieve objectives of teaching and learning.
3. Teachers should always engage themselves in on-the-job educational programme such as conference, seminars and workshop that will help to enhance their quality delivery of learning.
4. Teachers and learners should always develop and enhance positive relationship targeted towards promoting academic well-being of learners in school.

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